

3 E's of Emotional Freedom Technique In Pediatric Dentistry

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Received on: 28 - 05 - 2025; Accepted on: 04 - 06 - 2025; Published on : 07-07- 2025

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Abstract

Background : A child's successful dental appointment typically involves no tears. Many children often feel anxious or scared about dental exams and procedures. To help foster a positive outlook and reduce stress, different methods have been created, such as psychological approaches like Emotional Freedom Technique and Magnetic Finger Induction

Aim : The aim of the present study was to evaluate and compare the Emotional freedom technique and other anxiety management techniques used in paediatric dentistry

Material and methods : The research included 80 children aged 4 to 10. They were randomly divided into 3 experimental groups and one control group. Anxiety management methods such as the Emotional Freedom technique, Magnetic finger induction, and Tell show do were used for the respective experimental groups. The control group did not receive any interventions before their dental treatment. Anxiety levels were assessed using Venham's picture test before and after dental treatment, as well as by observing changes in blood pressure and pulse rate.

Result : After comparing the average variance between pre- and post-intervention levels across the 4 groups, it was noted that Group 1 (Emotional Freedom) showed the greatest reduction in anxiety levels, systolic and diastolic blood pressure and pulse rate. (as per Venham's Picture Test). Following this, Group 2 (Magnetic Induction) showed the next highest reduction, while Group 3 (Tell Show Do) exhibited the least reduction. Conclusion: Study finds that Emotional Freedom Technique is the most effective and cost-efficient method of managing fearful children in Paediatric dentistry.

Keywords : Emotional freedom technique, Magnetic finger induction, Tell show do, Behavior management.

Introduction

Dentistry can indeed be a triggering point for anxiety in both pediatric and adult patients. This anxiety, commonly known as dental anxiety or dental phobia, can stem from various factors, including fear of pain, past traumatic experiences, fear of needles or drills, embarrassment about the condition of one's teeth or a general fear of the dental environment. When it comes to pediatric dentistry, anxiety management becomes the key to a successful ministration for the treatment needed. Managing anxiety in children requires a comprehensive approach that addresses their unique needs and circumstances. By providing support, education, and appropriate interventions, parents, caregivers, and mental health professionals can help

children develop the skills and resilience needed to cope with anxiety effectively. There is not even a dentist who hasn't come across a very anxious, cantankerous, or screaming child during their time of practice. Over the years, anxiety has been addressed through a variety of approaches, pharmacological interventions, behavioral modeling processes, reinforcement/contingency approaches, physical restraint and additional kinds of distraction. Although the above methods have proven beneficial, ongoing experiments are being conducted to discover

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How to cite this article : Avani S et al. - 3 E's of Emotional Freedom Technique In Pediatric Dentistry, AJOCD-HT 2025

more advanced anxiety management techniques. One such innovation that allows anxiety control, emotional healing, and relief from various symptoms is the Emotional freedom technique. By applying pressure to acupuncture points, the emotional freedom technique incorporates facets of exposure therapy, somatic stimulation, and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), constituting a mind-body intervention. Frequently referred to as "tapping,"². Another psychological method that everyone has heard of but not practiced as such in dentistry at least once is hypnosis, this method also might show some promising results in children's anxiety management. Hypnosis involves inducing a trance-like state where individuals become highly suggestible and receptive to the suggestions of the hypnotist.³ Hypnosis can be a valuable tool in addressing certain issues in children, Since earlier days conventional methods have been also practiced in dentistry for the management of cranky children, and the most frequently used method is Tell-show-do technique. The tell phase involves an age appropriate explanation of the procedure which the dentist is going to do. The show phase is used to demonstrate a procedure up to the point where the instrument is performed. The do phase is then initiated and treatment is performed.

Material And Method : The study comprises 80 children of 4 to 10 years who visited the dental operator for the first time. The ethical committee approval was taken and the ethical clearance number was DJC/IEC/02/2021. The total subjects were divided randomly into 4 equal groups based on the anxiety management technique used. viz, Group 1, Emotional freedom technique group, Group 2, Magnetic finger induction, Group 3, Tell show do and Group 4 was taken as control.

The evaluation for anxiety has been done using vital stats like systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, pulse rate. Anxiety was evaluated using Venham's picture test. These evaluation was done pre and post intervention. All the subjects were evaluated for their behavior rating scale by frenkel's behavior rating scale prior to the study and the subjects falling under grade 3 and 4 were chosen as the candidates.

Evaluation of Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure And Anxiety Rates

The pulse rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure for each subject has been noted before and after the procedure. A visual version of Venham's picture test was displayed to the patient to gauge the anxiety component. The scale comprises 8 paired images. Each image depicted 2 figures, one displaying signs of anxiety and the other appearing non-anxious. The participants were given instructions to point out the figure they were most strongly attached to in every one of the paired pictures by gesturing at it. If the participant identified the concerned figure, they received a score of 1, while if they indicated the non-anxious figure, they obtained a score of 0. The total score is calculated by counting all the instances in which the youngster indicated a worried figure. Fig.1

Group 1, Procedure for anxiety management done by emotional freedom technique

The participants in the Emotional freedom technique group were initially instructed on the fundamentals of the technique's application. The subject is asked to consider their fear and provide a number on a scale of 0 to 10. A setup statement, such as "I have a fear of needles and I accept my fear and I wish to remove this fear from my mind," was made in accordance with the fear. The subject was guided through the tapping procedure by the operator. For instance, tapping on predefined tapping spots is done with the forefinger and middle fingertip of both hands. The places were the collar bone, underarm, karate chop point, forehead, underarm, beneath the eye, beneath the nose, and beneath the mouth. Following the demonstration, the participant was told to repeat the exercise on their own by focusing and relaxing at each area, receiving 7 to 9 taps. On a scale of 1 to 10, participants were asked to rate how uncomfortable they were expressing their feelings on their present anxiety after every EFT cycle. Sequential tapping was performed until the distress rate dropped to at least five points. Fig. 2

Group 2, Procedure for anxiety management done by magnetic finger induction method

Patients in the 2nd experimental group received the magnetic finger induction technique. The patient is instructed to close his or her eyes and take two breaths. They were then told to keep their hands straight in front of them and imagine that their forefingers were rotating in the direction of each other as though there was a magnet between them. The patient should count from 1 to 5 while performing this; their fingers will be so tightly held together that they will be unable to separate them even if they wanted to. In order to finally separate the fingers, the counting should be done in reverse, and the fingers should be removed slowly. Fig.3

Group 3, Procedure for anxiety management done by tell show do

Patients in the 3rd experimental group underwent tell show do. Fig. 4

Group 4, No anxiety management technique was done

There was no implementation of any anxiety management methods in the control group. Post-intervention assessments of Venham's anxiety rating, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and pulse rate were taken again after the particular patients had finished receiving the appropriate treatment.

Figure :1. Evaluation of anxiety using Venham's picture test

Figure : 2. Educating a patient how to do EFT

Figure : 3. Performing magnetic finger induction in a child patient

Figure : 4. Tell show do in a child patient

Results

On statistical analysis it was found that ,The mean change in the pulse rate ,in both systolic and diastolic blood pressure and the mean change in anxiety level evaluated by Venham's picture test shows maximum reduction after the intervention with Emotional freedom followed by the Magnetic finger induction and least by the Tell show do method. The pulse rate, blood pressure and anxiety measured by Venham’s picture test was raised in a statistically significant manner where no anxiety management technique was used. (Table 1,2,3,4)

Groups	Pre- Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	P value
Group 1 (Emotional Freedom)	111.45±7.70	79.35±7.95	32.10±9.29	0.001 (Sig)*
Group 2 (Magnetic Induction)	108.20±11.496	87.90±6.43	20.30±10.48	0.001 (Sig)*
Group 3 (TSD)	109.25±11.497	97.45±8.73	11.80±15.14	0.001 (Sig)*
Group 4 (Control)	107.55±9.907	111.60±6.84	-4.95±12.65	0.301 (non-Sig)

Table 1 : Mean values of pulse rate for various groups *p value <0.05

Groups	Pre- Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	P value
Emotional Freedom	2.55±1.39	1.00±0.72	1.55±1.39	*0.001 (Sig)
Magnetic Induction	2.85±0.81	2.15±0.87	0.70±0.81	*0.001 (Sig)
TSD	3.85±1.13	3.20±1.28	0.65±0.59	*0.001 (Sig)
Control	4.35±1.08	4.95±1.37	-0.60±1.08	0.283 (non-Sig)

Table 2 : Mean values of venham’s picture test for various groups

Groups	Pre Intervention	Post Intervention	Mean Change	P Value			
				Diastolic blood pressure	Systolic blood pressure	Diastolic blood pressure	Systolic blood pressure
Emotional freedom technique	112.25±6.78	72.45±9.47	97.00±5.32	61.80±7.12	15.25±9.90	10.65±8.06	Sig*
Magnetic induction	110.45±5.01	74.85±7.08	105.10±3.94	68.55±7.81	5.35±6.54	6.30±9.72	Sig*
TSD	110.60±6.15	77.00±2.53	107.30±3.24	74.90±5.03	3.25±4.97	2.10±3.85	Sig*
Control	111.60±7.34	74.40±7.08	112.15±7.61	77.75±2.93	-0.55±4.24	-3.35±6.59	Non - Sig

Table 3 : Mean Values of Systolic And Diastolic Blood Pressure For Various Groups

Discussion

A person with dental anxiety is described as aroused and prepared for anything to happen, with a generalized uneasiness associated with unusual situations. 4 . Twenty percent of adults experience dental anxiety, and half of them report having had a dread of dental operations as a child. (Locker et al., 1999) 5 According to a study published in 2021⁶ by Grisolia BM et al., dental anxiety primarily affects children. The cumulative prevalence of dental anxiety in children was 23.9%. The pooled prevalences for preschoolers, school-age children, and teenagers were 35.5%, 25.8%, and 13.3%, in that order. A child's incapacity or difficulty communicating and participating during dental treatment and the imparting of oral hygiene instructions are examples of behavioral management concerns that may arise from fear and anxiety during dental consultations. A doorway to paediatric dentistry's anxiety-free, laid-back treatment environment was made possible by behavior management. Anxiety management techniques have been used since ages to some extent but still the prevalence for fear and anxiety is increasing day by day. For a stress free dental treatment the demand for the need of an innovative effective and efficient distraction technique which will reduce the fear in children and in turn making the treatment fun filled and play full is very much necessary. The emotional freedom technique is one of its kind which is a psychological technique based on energy flow and distortion of energy lines in the body. EFT consists of three components: imaginal exposure, cognitive restructuring, and tapping on acupressure points to promote relaxation. This procedure aids in lowering anxiety and fear. According to Taylor et al. (2001) 7, EFT (Emotional Freedom Technique) provides benefits not only because of its physical tapping process but also because of its psychological mechanisms.⁷ By engaging in the tapping process, individuals can focus on the traumatic event and expose themselves to various aspects of it through imagination. This repeated exposure may have the effect of desensitizing the distress associated with traumatic memories. According to the findings of Cabyoglou et al. (2006)⁸, activating meridian points raises serotonin, beta-endorphin, endomorphin-1, and enkephalin levels in brain tissue and plasma, which has a sedative effect. Based on a 2003 study by Wells, Polglase, Andrews, Carrington, & Baker, people with phobias could successfully lower their stress and anxiety levels by using EFT⁹. Furthermore, anecdotal evidence points to the potential benefits of EFT in the treatment of anxiety disorders. Research by Carrington and Craig (2000)¹⁰, and Hartman-Kent (1999a, 1999b)¹¹ produced encouraging results. In medical psychiatric practice, EFT is often employed in conjunction with other interventions as an adjunctive therapy, as observed by E.H. Boath in (2012)¹². No such study has been done in dentistry to find the relevance of anxiety reduction using Emotional freedom technique. This has been very well found in our study which shows that maximum reduction of blood pressure and pulse rate has been seen when emotional freedom technique was used as an intervention pre and post. The statistical analysis confirmed that the Emotional Freedom Technique group exhibited a more

favorable mean change, The decrease in anxiety is attributed to the balance between the right hemisphere, which mediates the person's whole experience, and the left hemisphere of the brain, which is mostly linguistic and analytical. Greater suggestibility results from the intellectual hemisphere not developing to the point where it interferes with the proper operation of the holistic analogue hemisphere during childhood. In contrast to previous methods, Emmanuel BJ (2020)¹³ stated that pedodontists can effectively use magnetic finger induction in conjunction with careful patient planning and selection to affect a child's thinking towards treatment, promoting a positive mentality. Hypnosis may help reduce children's discomfort and anxiety during dental procedures, according to research. Calipel et al. (2005)¹⁴ compared the effects of midazolam and hypnosis on children undergoing surgery; the hypnosis group showed lower levels of anxiety. Furthermore, Gokli et al. (1994)¹⁵ reported that children undergoing local anesthesia under hypnosis cried less.

Although magnetic finger induction gives good results in anxiety management, magnetic finger induction performed to a lesser degree than emotional freedom technique in our study. On the other hand, magnetic finger induction produced better outcomes when evaluated using tell show do.

Conclusion

Given the study's boundaries, anxiety was reduced in subjects when evaluated by measuring systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, pulse rate and VPT most efficiently when using Emotional freedom technique followed by Magnetic finger induction and least by the Tell show do method.

Henceforth Emotional freedom technique is found to be the most efficient, effective and economical method in paediatric dentistry for the management of a fearful child

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